

Table 2. Effect of *A. niger* AN27 and its bioformulation Kalisena SD on sheath blight of rice.

Treatment	Infected tillers (%)	Disease reduction over control (%)	Lesion height (%)
Seed dressing	63.7	32.9	66.7
<i>Kalisena</i> SD	(52.95) ^a	(34.87)	(54.76)
Sheath spray	83.8	12.2	72.3
<i>A. niger</i> AN27	(66.28)	(20.32)	(58.24)
Untreated, inoculated	98.0	0.0	81.2
	(78.62)	(4.05)	(64.32)
Untreated, uninoculated	0.0	0.0	—
	(4.05)	(4.05)	(4.05)
CD at <i>P</i> = 0.05	3.14	3.30	2.09

^aNumbers in parentheses are arcsine-transformed values.

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Influence of rice varieties on parasitism of the African rice gall midge (AfRGM)

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The African rice gall midge (AfRGM), *Orseolia oryzivora* Harris & Gagné (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae), is a major constraint to rainfed and irrigated lowland rice production in Africa. The most common natural enemies associated with AfRGM are the polyembryonic endoparasitoid *Platygaster diplosisae* Risbec (Hymenoptera: Platygasteridae) and the solitary ectoparasitoid *Aprostocetus procerae* Risbec (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae). These species have potential as biological control agents against AfRGM (Williams et al 1997). The extent to which the activity of these parasitoids may be influenced by rice genotype is not well known. This is a crucial issue because the effects of resistance factor(s) in the rice genotype on the developing midge larvae are likely to be exhibited on the next trophic level of association, i.e., on the AfRGM parasitoids. Such interactions are known to exist in maize, sorghum, and other crops (Potting et al 1995, Nwanze and Nwilene 1998).

Some natural enemies are known to base their foraging strategies on plant volatiles that mediate searching behavior, especially at longer distances. Plant resistance to insects can result from antagonism due to the presence of chemicals in vari-

ous plant tissues. To optimize the benefits from integrating the breeding for resistance to AfRGM and biological control, it is desirable that these management options be either complementary or synergistic and not antagonistic.

A trial was carried out in 1998 at the Ebonyi State College of Agriculture greenhouse in the Ikwo local government area, near Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, southeast Nigeria. Ikwo is in the forest/savanna transition zone. The AfRGM and its parasitoids *P. diplosisae* and *A. procerae* were reared in seedboxes in the greenhouse (25–30 °C temperature and 50–90% relative humidity). The cultures had been maintained for 4 wk prior to the experiments. Four rice varieties showing different levels of resistance—ITA306 (susceptible), Cisadane (tolerant), NHTA8 (partially resistant), and Eguazankpa (widely grown traditional variety in the middle belt of Nigeria) (Williams et al 1997)—were used to determine whether these differences in resistance affected parasitism of *P. diplosisae* and *A. procerae*.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. About 80 seedlings in each seedbox were exposed to 10 gravid

female and 5 male AfRGM at 12 d after seeding. Two days after AfRGM infestation, twenty 1-d-old gravid females of *P. diplosisae* were released in each box. Two weeks after AfRGM infestation, when pupation commenced, twenty 1-d-old gravid females of *A. procerae* were released in each box. (Separate boxes were infested with *P. diplosisae* and *A. procerae*.) Four weeks after parasitoid introduction, 40 plants per box were dissected and data on the following were recorded: tillers with galls, total tillers, number of larvae/pupae collected from galls, number of larvae/pupae parasitized, and percent parasitism. Data were subjected to analysis of variance.

Under no-choice conditions, in the experiment with *A. procerae*, AfRGM infestation of partially resistant variety NHTA8 was significantly lower than that of ITA306 and Cisadane at 50 d after crop emergence (Fig. 1). In the experiment with *P. diplosisae*, however, the four varieties did not differ in levels of AfRGM infestation. There was no significant difference in the number of larvae/pupae parasitized, and percent parasitism by both parasitoids was also consistently high in the four varieties (see figure). Both parasitoids attacked almost every gall that was infested. The

Effect of rice varieties on the parasitism of AfRGM by *Platygaster diplosisae* and *Aprostocetus procerae* and the percentage of tillers with galls. Means (\pm S.E.) within a row for each parasitoid followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P>0.05$; least significant difference.

high level of parasitism in the four varieties suggests that host plants offer no antagonistic effects to AfRGM parasitoids. The plant resistance factors in NHTA8 and Eguazankpa did not influence parasitoid activity or level of parasitism under no-choice conditions, indicating that the interaction between host-plant resistance and AfRGM parasitoids would thus be synergistic or additive and could result in successful integration of these two important pest management options. This is particularly important in the integrated pest management of AfRGM for which desirable levels of resistance have not yet been achieved.

Results, however, might differ under free-choice conditions. Tritrophic interactions should be explored by plant breeders and insect ecologists who aim to produce resistant varieties which, when infested, still produce volatiles in sufficient amounts to attract parasitoids or preda-

tors. With recent advances in hybridization and molecular markers at WARDA, efforts are under way to increase rice resistance and understanding of such tritrophic interactions in cereal-based ecosystems.

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Ecological characterization of biotic constraints to rice in Cambodia

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From 1994 to 1998, a total of 73 rainfed lowland rice fields (RLR) (>0.3 ha each) in Cambodia were studied to determine which pests affect yields and how cropping practices affect pest levels. From 1997 to 2000, this information was used to generate testable hypotheses for crop protection research and to help prioritize the integrated pest management (IPM) research program of CIAP. The data collection methods of Savary et al (1996) were adapted to Cambodian conditions. “Pests” included insects, weeds, and diseases. Farmer interviews (Jahn et al 1997b), pest collections, and practical considerations (e.g., ease of recognizing the pest or its damage) were used to determine which pests to include

in the study. Pesticides were not used in any of the fields in this study.

Data were gathered at four crop development stages: tillering, booting, milk, and maturity. The yield of each field was estimated by averaging the weights of three randomly selected $2 \times 5\text{-m}^2$ harvested areas, converted to t ha^{-1} and adjusted to 14% moisture. Pest incidence was recorded from 10 hills chosen haphazardly from each field. Weed infestation was measured as the percentage weed cover in three 1-m^2 areas that included sampling hill number 3, 6, and 9. The analysis proceeded in five steps: (1) determination of average injury levels of each pest for each crop stage, (2) categorization of variables (i.e.,

pest, cropping practices, and yield) into classes, (3) testing for independence of paired variables (i.e., pest levels, cropping practices, and yields) in contingency tables, (4) clustering of cropping practices, yields, and pest profiles, and (5) development of contingency tables and correspondence analysis. Data were analyzed with Excel® and STAT-ITCF®.

Correspondence analysis between combined variables (i.e., cropping practices and pest profiles) and yields resulted in the formation of four domains (see figure). Low levels of gall midge damage (i.e., 0–0.2% tiller damage) were recorded in the highest yielding fields (domain D, table). The lowest yielding fields had high